

Estimation of Glycine, Alanine and Lysine and their Metal Complexes with Chloramine-T

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Chloramine-T oxidizes glycine and lysine with a six-electron change in pH 5.0 and 4.0 buffer media respectively, while alanine undergoes a four-electron oxidation with this reagent in pH 5.5 buffer. The analytical methods are useful for the estimation of amino-acids and their metal complexes in solution, by back titration procedures. Para toluene sulphonamide, cyanates and nitriles have been detected among the reaction products.

CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) has attracted considerable attention recently, as a new oxidimetric reagent. As a part of our chloraminometric investigations of biochemical compounds and their metal complexes¹⁻⁵, we have examined the behaviour of CAT towards glycine, alanine and lysine. Although these aminoacids are oxidized by CAT in different acid media, stoichiometric oxidation with a six-electron change per molecule was indicated for glycine and lysine in buffer media of pH 5 and 4 respectively, while a four-electron stoichiometry was obtained with alanine around pH 5.5. Since the reaction rate was not rapid enough for a direct titration of the aminoacid with CAT, back titration procedures have been developed. The present communication also reports the estimation of zinc, cadmium, barium, strontium, manganese, nickel, silver and copper complexes of glycine, zinc and barium complexes of lysine and a nickel complex of alanine using CAT.

Experimental

Chromatographically pure glycine (Reanal, Hungary), lysine hydrochloride (V. P. Chest Institute, New Delhi) and DL-alanine (Loba-chemic, Austria) were further recrystallized from aqueous solution and the purity was checked by the acetous-perchloric acid method⁶. Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified by the method of Morris *et al*⁷ and an approximately decinormal aqueous solution was standardized by the iodometric method.

Solutions of the aminoacids (~2 mg/ml) were prepared in appropriate buffers and solvents. Compounds of accepted grades of purity were used in preparing other solutions.

Infrared spectra of samples (KBr disc) were obtained on a Carl-Zeiss UR-10 Infrared spectrophotometer.

The following salts and complexes of glycine⁸⁻¹² and alanine¹³ were prepared by standard methods reported in literature.

- I. Bis(glycinato) zinc(II), monohydrate
 $\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- II. Bis(glycinato) cadmium(II), monohydrate
 $\text{Cd}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- III. Bis(glycine)-barium(II) dichloride, monohydrate
 $(\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-)_2 \text{BaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- IV. Bis(glycine)-strontium(II) dichloride, trihydrate
 $(\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-)_2 \text{SrCl}_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- V. Bis(glycine)-manganese(II) dichloride
 $(\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-)_2 \text{MnCl}_2$
- VI. Bis(glycinato) nickel(II), dihydrate
 $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- VII. (Glycine) silver(I) nitrate
 $(\text{NH}_3^+\text{CH}_2\text{COO}^-) \text{AgNO}_3$
- VIII. Bis(glycinato)-copper(II), monohydrate
 $\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- IX. Bis(alaninato) nickel(II), dihydrate
 $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{CHNH}_2\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- X. Bis(lysinato)-zinc(II) monohydrate
 $\text{Zn}[\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{CHNH}_2\text{COO}]_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
- XI. Bis(lysine) barium(II) dichloride, monohydrate
 $[\text{NH}_3^+(\text{CH}_2)_4\text{CHNH}_2\text{COO}^-]_2 \text{BaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

The lysine complexes were prepared by mixing the amino-acid with ZnO (complex X) or with $\text{BaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (complex XI) in 2:1 molar ratio, evaporating on a water bath and followed by recrystallization from 50% v/v alcohol-water mixture (complex X) or from aqueous solution (complex XI).

The composition of the lysine complexes was checked by elemental analyses and infrared spectral data¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

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TABLE 3—ESTIMATION OF METAL COMPLEXES* OF GLYCINE, ALANINE AND LYSINE WITH CHLORAMINE-T

CAT taken : 2.5 m. mole

Temp : 26° (40° for lysine complexes)

(The amounts are expressed in mg)

I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI										
4.28	4.21	4.22	4.07	4.08	4.13	4.16	4.04	4.03	4.03	4.05	10.28	10.32	2.32	2.34	3.84	3.82	4.40	4.44	4.26	4.23
10.70	10.67	10.52	10.51	10.18	10.20	10.32	10.36	10.10	10.13	10.08	30.84	30.95	11.62	11.65	19.20	19.21	22.00	22.09	21.30	21.30
32.10	32.14	31.56	31.62	30.53	30.69	30.97	31.01	30.31	30.33	30.25	30.38	41.12	41.06	17.43	17.42	28.80	28.76	33.00	33.09	32.08
42.80	42.80	42.02	40.70	40.74	41.30	41.30	40.42	40.46	40.34	40.41	51.40	51.48	23.24	23.31	38.40	38.62	44.00	44.18	42.60	42.60

- * I. Bis (glycinato) zinc (II), monohydrate ;
- II. Bis (glycinato) cadmium (II), monohydrate ;
- III. Bis (glycine)-barium (II) dichloride, monohydrate ;
- IV. Bis (glycine)-strontium (II) dichloride, trihydrate ;
- V. Bis (glycine)-manganese (II) dichloride ;
- VI. Bis (glycinato) nickel (II), dihydrate ;
- VII. (Glycine)-silver (I) nitrate ;
- VIII. Bis (glycinato)-copper (II), monohydrate ;
- IX. Bis (alaninato) nickel (II), dihydrate ;
- X. Bis (lysinate)-zinc (II), monohydrate ;
- XI. Bis (lysine)-barium (II) dichloride monohydrate.

From investigations with the complexes, the time required for a stoichiometric oxidation of the ligand in the buffer media mentioned above was determined:

Complex I (30 min.); II, IV and VII (45 min.); III, V and VI (60 min.); VIII (75 min.); IX (90 min.); X (150 min. at 26° or 45 min. at 40°); XI (90 min. at 40°).

Oxidation of lysine complexes was found to be sluggish at room temperature (26°) and the determinations were completed at 40°.

Recommended procedure :

A solution of the aminoacid or its metal complex (~2 mg/ml) in acetate buffer (pH 5 for glycine and its complexes, pH 5.5 for alanine and its complexes and pH 4 for lysine and its complexes) was prepared. Aliquots of the solution (~4-30 mg) were added to a measured excess of 0.1N CAT (~2.5 m mole) in an iodine flask at room temperature (40° for lysine complexes). The mixture was shaken occasionally and after a known interval of time as mentioned under preliminary studies, 10 ml. of 2NH₂SO₄, 20 ml of 20% KI and 10-20 ml. of water were added and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulphate using starch indicator. A blank titration was carried out with CAT solution alone.

Copper ion interferes during the back titration of complex VIII. Hence the analytical procedure was modified as follows : Aliquots of the complex solution were added to a known excess of 0.1N CAT as above. After 75 minutes, 60 ml. of 0.1N ascorbic acid, 5 ml. of 0.1M EDTA, 5 ml. of 2NH₂SO₄ and 2 ml. of starch-KI mixture were added. The excess of ascorbic acid was then titrated against 0.05N CAT, to the appearance of a pale blue colour. A blank titration was carried out with the same volumes of CAT, ascorbic acid and EDTA solutions against 0.05N CAT.

Results and Discussion

Tables 2 and 3 show some typical results of analyses of aminoacids and their metal complexes with CAT. It is seen that the maximum error in estimation is within 0.5%.

The six-electron stoichiometry observed with glycine and lysine in the free state as well as in their complexes can be shown as follows :

Here R = *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂, R' is H for glycine and NH₂(CH₂)₄ - for lysine. M = Zn or Cd or Ni or Cu and M' = Ba or Sr or Mn.

Oxidation of alanine and its complex can be indicated as follows :

The presence of *p*-toluene sulphonamide among the reaction products was detected by paper chromatography. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ethanol as the spray reagent (R_F=0.905). The cyanates formed in reactions (1) to (4) were detected by the Werner's test¹⁷. The presence of nitrile (equations 5 and 6) in the reaction products was detected by its colour reaction with hydroxylamine and ferric chloride¹⁸.

Interference by allied compounds and foreign ions was investigated. Aminoacids such as cystine, methionine and valine interfered seriously with the estimation of glycine, lysine and alanine, while Na⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ ions (up to 0.1 m mole) had no effect on the rate or stoichiometry of oxidation.

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